

ISSUES OF IMPROVING INFRASTRUCTURE TO INCREASE THE INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN

Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich

PhD Independent researcher of Fergana State Technical University

Tel: +998(33)000-44-77

e-mail: iataisamtov@bk.ru

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1233-4561>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15188769>

Abstract

This thesis analyzes the factors that negatively affect the investment attractiveness of production-specialized free economic zones operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, identifies the main factors, and proposes positive changes that serve to increase the investment attractiveness of free economic zones.

Keywords: investment, infrastructure, free economic zone, efficiency, global economy, competition, preferential tax, specialized regions, economic indicators.

Introduction

Free economic zones (FEZ) occupy a special place in the economic development of Uzbekistan. These zones play an important role in strengthening the country's integration into the global economic system, creating a favorable environment for investors, and ensuring economic growth. Free economic zones increase their competitiveness in the global market with such features as special tax and customs benefits, freedom in the production and service sectors, innovative approaches, and infrastructure development.

However, the factors determining the investment attractiveness of free economic zones are numerous and interconnected. On the one hand, they are influenced by such factors as the economic and political stability of the region, market infrastructure, legal framework, and tax policy. On the other hand, innovative approaches, which play an important role in attracting highly qualified personnel, modern technologies, and investments, are also an important factor in making personal and general investment decisions.

At the same time, analyzing the effectiveness of the existing system and developing practical proposals to increase the investment attractiveness of free economic zones of Uzbekistan is a pressing issue. This thesis analyzes the factors influencing the investment attractiveness of free economic zones of Uzbekistan, their changes and development prospects.

Issues of increasing the investment attractiveness of regions have been studied by many domestic and foreign scientists. In economic literature, there are various interpretations of the concept of "investment attractiveness," most of which are aimed at expressing the ability and potential of the region to attract

investments. In particular, G.A. Alexander interprets investment attractiveness as a set of favorable conditions for investors[1], V.V. Litvinova expresses it through the level of socio-economic development of the region and the ratio of investment risks[2]. Researchers from Uzbekistan, such as D. Gozibekov, N. Khaydarov, B. Salimov, studied the methodological foundations of the formation of a regional investment environment[3].

In the research process, such methods as systemic and comparative analysis were widely used. Also, the rating method and a multi-criteria assessment methodology were used to assess the investment attractiveness of the regions. Empirical data were obtained from official reports of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade, as well as international organizations.

One of the important directions of Uzbekistan's economic policy is the comprehensive creation of free economic zones and the creation of new jobs based on the attraction of foreign investment. In 2008-2016, three free economic zones were created in the country, and in recent years their number has reached 24. Currently, there are 15 free production zones, 6 pharmaceutical zones, 2 tourism zones, and 1 free economic zone operating in the agricultural and innovative directions in the republic.

There are several problems affecting the investment attractiveness of free economic zones of Uzbekistan:

The variability of laws and regulations:

Laws and regulations for free economic zones change frequently. This creates uncertainty for investors, as they must constantly adapt to new rules.

The complexity of the tax and customs system:

Tax and customs benefits are sometimes very complex, which can be confusing and difficult for investors. In particular, the complexity of benefits and tax rates hinders the attraction of some investors.

Insufficiency of infrastructure:

Infrastructure (roads, energy, communications, etc.) in free economic zones is underdeveloped in some places. This complicates production and increases costs.

Absence of information about free economic zones for investors:

For an investor to make a decision, it is necessary, first of all, to obtain sufficient information about the country and free economic zones in it, as well as the benefits provided to them:

For investors, the process of entering the free economic zone is closed and takes a long time:

The time required to submit documents and make decisions to become a member of the FEZ for any investor wishing to invest:

To solve these problems, the government is carrying out a number of reforms. If these issues are resolved, Uzbekistan's free economic zones will help attract more investments and increase economic growth.

The fact that large funds are spent on infrastructure improvement in the most important and almost all of the above-mentioned free economic zones shows that there is a need for even more infrastructure.

There are several problems related to infrastructure in free economic zones, including: First of all, the lack of a transport and road network. In some free economic zones, transport infrastructure (roads, railways) is underdeveloped. This, in turn, creates difficulties in transporting and delivering products, which increases production costs.

Secondly, energy supply. Shortage and disruption of electricity and other energy resources in free economic zones. This reduces production efficiency and creates additional costs for companies.

Thirdly, problems in water supply and sewerage systems. In some free economic zones, there are shortcomings in clean water supply and sewerage systems. This situation is especially related to the lack of water sources necessary for agriculture or the industrial sector.

Fourthly, the insufficient development of logistics and warehouse facilities. In some zones, the logistics system and warehouse facilities are insufficient. This complicates the processes of storage and transportation of products, and also increases delivery times.

Today, to solve these problems, efforts are being made to improve infrastructure, provide the necessary energy resources, and develop the transport system, which, in turn, will serve to improve the investment attractiveness of free economic zones.

Today, countries are implementing a number of reforms aimed at improving legal, economic, and infrastructural conditions for attracting investment, creating tax incentives, developing international cooperation, supporting the innovation environment, and training a qualified workforce. All these measures serve to ensure the economic growth of countries and their integration into the global market.

To increase the investment attractiveness of free economic zones operating in Uzbekistan, it is important to work primarily on improving infrastructure. To

improve infrastructure in free economic zones, it is advisable to carry out the following important work:

Firstly, international financial institutions (for example, the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development) can provide loans, grants, or investments to finance infrastructure projects of free economic zones.

Secondly, the necessary infrastructure for free economic zones can also be financed by the private sector. Private companies, foreign and local investors will attract capital for the construction and development of infrastructure facilities. For example, in Singapore, many infrastructure projects were implemented by the private sector. Cooperation between the state and the private sector is at a very high level. Public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms are widely used in Singapore for infrastructure development.

Thirdly, attracting international investments and direct investments. For the development of infrastructure in free economic zones, it is possible to attract foreign direct investment. Investors are especially ready to invest in infrastructure projects that provide access to global markets. Free economic zones in Dubai, for example, are financed by many international investors. Foreign investments make up the majority of infrastructure projects in Dubai.

Fourth, the use of public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms. The use of public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms can be an effective solution for the development of the infrastructure of free economic zones. Through PPP, the public and private sectors can jointly finance and implement infrastructure projects. For example, in India, the infrastructure of free economic zones is developing through the public-private partnership (PPP) mechanism. Many successful infrastructure projects based on PPP have also been implemented in countries such as Australia and Great Britain.

Fifthly, attracting international grants and donor funds. International organizations, donors, and management assistants can provide grants or economic assistance for infrastructure projects in free economic zones. This method is especially important for developing countries. For example, some countries in South Asia have received grants from the World Bank and other donor organizations to help develop the infrastructure of free economic zones. Funds for infrastructure improvement in free economic zones will be attracted from various sources, including the state budget, international financial institutions, the private sector, public-private partnerships, international grants and bonds. Global experience shows that cooperation between the public and private sectors, as well as assistance from international financial institutions and investors, is of great importance in infrastructure development.

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